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DETERMENATION OF SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION HPLC METHOD FOR ELITRAGRAVIR, TENOFOVIR DISPROXIL FUMARATE, EMTRICITABINE AND COBICISTAT ITS BULK AND TABLET DOSAGE FORM.

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ABSTRACT

A New method was established for simultaneous estimation of Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat by RP-HPLC method. Chromatographic separations were carried using Inertsil ODS (4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m) column with a mobile phase composition of 0.1% OPA buffer and Acetonitrile(30:70) have been delivered at a flow rate of 1ml/min and the detection was carried out using waters HPLC auto sampler, separation module 2695 with PDA detector 2996 at wavelength 252 nm. The retention time for Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat were 2.287, 2.957, 5.652 and 9.801 minute respectively. The correlation coefficient values in linearity were found to be 0.999 and concentration range 75-225 μ g/ml for Elvitegravir, 150-450 μ g/ml for Tenofovir, 100-300 μ g/ml for Emtricitabine and 75-225 μ g/ml for Cobicistat respectively. For accuracy the total recovery was found to be 100.11%, 100.26, 100.64 and 100.08% for Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat respectively. The LOD and LOQ for Elvitegravir was found to be 2.98 and 9.98, LOD and LOQ for Tenofovir was found to be 3.02 and 10.02, LOD and LOQ for Emtricitabine was found to be 3.00 and 10.00 and LOD and LOQ for Cobicistat was found to be 3.00 and 10.02. The force degradation studies were performed for the dosage form and the results are within the limits. The results of study showed that the proposed RP-HPLC method is a simple, accurate, precise, rugged, robust, fast and reproducible, which may be useful for the routine estimation of Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat in pharmaceutical dosage form.

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INTRODUCTION

Emtricitabine Emtricitabine (EMT) is synthetic deoxycytidine analogue and has been approved as an anti-retroviral agent in the treatment of HIV-type 1 infections [1,2]. It is a nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor that competitively inhibits the HIV reverse transcriptase enzyme and blocks the HIV replication. The chemical name of the EMT (Figure 1) is 5-fluoro-1-[(2*R*,5*S*)-2(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-yl]cytosine[3].

Elvitegravir Elvitegravir (ELV) is a novel class of anti-retroviral agents, belongs to integrase strand transferase inhibitor, inhibits the integrase enzyme and prevents the virus replication [4]. The chemical name of ELV (Figure 2) is 6(3-chloro-2-fluorobenzyl)-1-[(2*S*)-1-hydroxy-3-methylbutane-2-yl]-7-methoxy-4-oxo-1,4-dihydroquinoline-3-carboxylic acid .

Cobicistat Cobicistat (COB) was used in patients with HIV infection. Co-administration of COB (Figure 3) inhibits the cytochrome p450 3A4 enzyme and helps in improving bioavailability and half-life of ELV in HIV-infected patients [5–7]. Cobicistat acts as an HIV integrase inhibitor. Chemical name of Cobicistat is Thiazol-5-ylmethyl N-[1-benzyl-4-[[2-[[2-isopropylthiazol-4-yl)methyl-methyl-carbamoyl] amino]-4-morpholinobutanoyl] amino]-5-phenyl-pentyl] carbamate (Figure 3).

Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate belongs to a class of antiretroviral drugs known as nucleotide analogue reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NRTIs). Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (TNDF) is an adenine derivative and is a pro-drug of tenofovir, chemically known as 9-[(*R*)[(bis)[(isopropoxy carbonyl)oxy]-phosphinyl]methoxy]propyl adenine fumarate. It blocks the HIV reverse transcriptase enzyme and incorporated into viral DNA[8]. Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate is a prodrug form of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate. Chemical name of Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate is ({[(2*R*)-1-(6-amino-9H-purin-9-yl) propan-2-yl] oxy} methyl) phosphonic acid (Figure.4). Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate blocks reverse transcriptase, a crucial virus enzyme in human immunodeficiency virus 1 (HIV-1) and hepatitis B virus infections.

Fig no : 1 Structure of Emtricitabine.

Fig no : 2 Structure of Elitragravir.

Fig no : 3 Structure of Cobicistat.

Fig no : 4 Structure of Tenofovir DF.

Several methods have been published for the determination of Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat by thin layer chromatography (TLC)[9], UV spectrophotometry[9-12] and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)[12-21] in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. However, a simple, robust, simultaneous method that helpful for the separation of four drugs in a single run is of prime importance. In view of the paucity of information, present study was conducted with an objective of development and validation of a simple reverse phase liquid chromatography (RPHPLC) method for the simultaneous determination of Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat in its bulk and tablet dosage forms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Chemicals and Reagents:**

Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat were supplied by Hetero labs, Hyderabad. Dosage form was purchased by Local Pharmacy. Ortho phosphoric acid was analytical grade supplied by Finer chemical LTD, Mumbai, Water and Methanol for HPLC LICHROSOLV (MERCCK)

Equipment and Chromatographic Conditions:

The chromatography was performed on a Waters 2695 HPLC system, equipped with an auto sampler, PDA detector and Empower 2 software. Analysis was carried out at 252 nm with an Inertsil ODS (4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m) dimensions at ambient temperature. The optimized mobile phase consists of 0.1% OPA and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 30:70 v/v. Flow rate was maintained at 1 ml/min and run time for 15 min.

Preparation of solutions:**Preparation of buffer:**

Take 1 ml of ortho phosphoric acid in 1000 ml volumetric flask and make up to the mark with HPLC water and sonicate for 15 minutes then filter through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Mix a mixture of above buffer 300 mL (30%) and 700 mL of Acetonitrile HPLC (70%) degas in ultrasonic water bath for 5 minutes. Filter through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration

The diluents:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Preparation of standard stock solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 75 mg of Elvitegravir, 150 mg of Tenofovir, 100 mg of Emtricitabine and 75 mg of Cobicistat working standard into a 100 ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 70 mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution) Further pipette 2 ml of the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Sample stock solution:

Accurately weigh 10 tablets crush in mortar and pestle and transfer tablet powder equivalent to 75 mg of Elvitegravir, 150 mg of Tenofovir, 100 mg of Emtricitabine and 75 mg of Cobicistat working standard into a 100 ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 70 mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution) Further pipette 2 ml of the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Procedure:

Inject 20 μ L of the standard, sample into the chromatographic system and measure the areas for Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat peaks and calculate the % Assay by using the formulae.

Preparation of Stock

Accurately weigh and transfer 75 mg of Elvitegravir, 150 mg of Tenofovir, 100 mg of Emtricitabine and 75 mg of Cobicistat working standard into a 100 ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 70 mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

METHOD:**System suitability parameters:**

To evaluate system suitability parameters such as retention time, tailing factor and USP theoretical plate count, the mobile phase was allowed to flow through the column at a flow rate of 1ml/min for 15 minutes to equilibrate the column at ambient temperature. Chromatographic separation was achieved by injecting a volume of 20 μ L of standard into Inertsil ODS (4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m), the mobile phase of composition 0.1% OPA buffer and acetonitrile in the (30:70) was allowed to flow through the column at a flow rate of 1ml per minute. Retention time, tailing factor and USP theoretical plate count of the developed method are shown in table 1.

Assay of pharmaceutical formulation:

The proposed validated method was successfully applied to determine Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat in their tablet dosage form. The result obtained for Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat was comparable with the corresponding labeled amounts and they were shown in Table-2.

Validation of Analytical method:**Linearity and Range:**

Stock solution was prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat in 100 ml of diluent and further diluted to the required concentrations with diluent. The solution was prepared at five concentration levels ranging from 75µg/ml to 225µg/ml of Elvitegravir, 150µg/ml to 450µg/ml of Tenofovir, 100µg/ml to 300µg/ml of Emtricitabine and 75µg/ml to 225µg/ml of Cobicistat. Inject each level into the chromatographic system and measure the peak area. Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and calculate the correlation coefficient. The results are shown in table 3 & 4.

Accuracy studies:

The accuracy was determined by help of recovery study. The recovery method carried out at three level 50%, 100%, 150%. Inject the standard solutions into chromatographic system. Calculate the Amount found and Amount added for Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values.

Precision Studies:

Precision was calculated from Coefficient of variance for six replicate injections of the standard. The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six Injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found. The results are shown in table 5.

Ruggedness:

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method, Precision was performed on different day. The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found. The results are shown in table 6.

Robustness:

As part of the Robustness, deliberate change in the Flow rate, Mobile Phase composition, Temperature Variation was made to evaluate the impact on the method. The flow rate was varied at 0.8 ml/min to 1.2ml/min. The Organic composition in the Mobile phase was varied from 63% to 77%.

LOD and LOQ:

The sensitivity of RP-HPLC was determined from LOD and LOQ. Which were calculated from the calibration curve using the following equations as per ICH guidelines.

Force degradation Studies:

The International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guideline entitled stability testing of new drug substances and products requires that stress testing be carried out to elucidate the inherent stability characteristics of the active substance. The aim of this work was to perform the stress degradation studies on the Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat using the proposed method.

Hydrolytic Degradation under Acidic Condition

Pipette 2.0 ml of above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and 3 ml of 0.1N HCl was added. Then, the volumetric flask was kept at 60°C for 6 hours and then neutralized with 0.1 N NaOH and make up to 10ml with diluent. Filter the solution with 0.22 microns syringe filters and place in vials.

Hydrolytic Degradation under Alkaline Condition

Pipette 2.0 ml of above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask into and add 3 ml of 0.1N NaOH was added in 10 ml of volumetric flask. Then, the volumetric flask was kept at 60°C for 6 hours and then neutralized with 0.1N HCl and make up to 10ml with diluent. Filter the solution with 0.22 microns syringe filters and place in vials.

Oxidative Degradation

Pipette 2.0 ml above stock solution-2 into a 10ml volumetric flask, 1 ml of 3% w/v of hydrogen peroxide added and the volume was made up to the mark with diluent. The volumetric flask was then kept at room temperature for 15 min. Filter the solution with 0.45 microns syringe filters and place in vials.

Thermal Induced Degradation

Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat sample was taken in petridish and kept in Hot air oven at 110°C for 24 hours. Then the sample was taken and diluted with diluents and injected into HPLC and analysed.

Photo degradation:

Pipette 2.0 ml above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and expose to sunlight for 24hrs and the volume was made up to the mark with diluent. Filter the solution with 0.45 microns syringe filters and place in vials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5: Standard chromatogram.

Figure 6: Sample chromatogram.

Figure 7: Blank chromatogram.

Table 1: System suitability parameters.

Parameters	Elvitegravir	Tenofovir	Emtricitabine	Cobicistat
Retention time	2.287	2.957	5.652	9.801
USP Plate count	3944	2963	5926	4461
USP Tailing	1.34	1.29	1.37	1.13
USP Resolution	--	3.19	10.49	12.25

Assay Calculation for Elvitegravir

$$\frac{62205}{62572} * \frac{75}{100} * \frac{2}{10} * \frac{100}{520} * \frac{10}{2} * \frac{1040}{150} * \frac{99.8}{100} * 100 = 99.21\%$$

Assay Calculation for Tenofovir

$$\frac{342646}{342646} * \frac{150}{100} * \frac{2}{10} * \frac{100}{520} * \frac{10}{2} * \frac{1040}{300} * \frac{99.8}{100} * 100 = 99.80\%$$

Assay Calculation for Emtricitabine

$$\frac{412362}{412363} * \frac{100}{100} * \frac{2}{10} * \frac{100}{520} * \frac{10}{2} * \frac{1040}{200} * \frac{99.8}{100} * 100 = 99.80\%$$

Assay Calculation for Cobicistat

$$\frac{37550}{37564} * \frac{75}{100} * \frac{2}{10} * \frac{100}{520} * \frac{10}{2} * \frac{1040}{150} * \frac{99.8}{100} * 100 = 99.84\%$$

Table 2: Assay results for Elvitegravir ,Tenofovir,Emtricitabine and Cobicistat.

	Label Claim (mg)	% Assay
Elitragravir	150	99.21
Tenofovir DF	300	99.80
Emtricitabine	200	99.80
Cobicistat	150	99.84

Table 3: Linearity results for Elvitegravir and Tenofovir.

Elvitegravir		Tenofovir	
Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Area	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Area
75	31158	150	174283
112.5	62501	225	346309
150	98431	300	534616
187.5	126883	375	738393
225	159437	450	910971
Correlation coefficient	0.999	Correlation coefficient	0.999

Table 4: Linearity results for Emtricitabine and Cobicistat.

Emtricitabine		Cobicistat	
Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Area	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Area
100	200028	75	19268
150	412844	112.5	37340
200	616857	150	55298
250	842986	187.5	74833
300	1052774	225	92106
Correlation coefficient	0.999	Correlation coefficient	0.999

Figure 8: Linearity graph for Elvitegravir.

Figure 9: Linearity graph for Tenofovir.

Figure 10: Linearity graph for Emtricitabine.

Figure 11: Linearity graph for Cobicistat.

Table 5: Precision results for Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat.

Injection	Elvitegravir	Tenofovir	Emtricitabine	Cobicistat
Injection-1	62521	340835	412366	37719
Injection-2	63501	345902	417933	37131
Injection-3	63131	340203	418246	37145
Injection-4	62349	343151	410461	37488
Injection-5	64024	341901	413907	37380
Injection-6	63398	341902	416726	37139
Average	63154	342315.7	414939.8	37333.67
Standard Deviation	630.252	2027.726	3188.463	240.421
%RSD	1	0.6	0.8	0.6

Table 6: Ruggedness results for Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat.

Injection	Elvitegravir	Paritprevir	Emtricitabine	Cobicistat
Injection-1	62421	350835	418366	38019
Injection-2	62501	345902	417933	37131
Injection-3	62131	349203	418246	37145
Injection-4	62349	343151	419461	37488
Injection-5	62024	349901	419907	37380
Injection-6	62398	346902	419726	37239
Average	62304	347649	418939.8	37400.33
Standard Deviation	185.3041	2880.244	854.3403	333.0499
%RSD	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.9

Table 7: Degradation results for Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat.

Parameters	Elvitegravir		Tenofovir		Emtricitabine		Cobicistat	
	Area	% Degraded	Area	% Degraded	Area	% Degraded	Area	% Degraded
Standard	62572		342646		412362.7		37550.7	
Acid	60297	3.64	331313	3.31	393095	4.67	35645	5.08
Base	60635	3.10	329952	3.70	399441	3.13	35835	4.57
Peroxide	60293	3.64	316915	7.51	396871	3.76	35209	6.24
Photo	601121	3.92	325902	4.89	380461	7.74	35488	5.49
Thermal	60121	3.76	325462	5.02	393431	4.59	35432	5.64

CONCLUSION

The proposed HPLC method was found to be simple, precise, accurate and sensitive for the simultaneous estimation of Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Hence, this method can easily and conveniently adopt for routine quality control analysis of Elvitegravir, Tenofovir, Emtricitabine and Cobicistat in pure and its pharmaceutical dosage forms.

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